
INNOVATIVE METHOD FOR IOT BASED PRODUCTION DETECTION SYSTEM USING ARDUINO

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ABSTRACT

In recent systems whenever we scan the product, its basic information is stored in its local database. But by using IOT whenever we scan the product by using the RFID card the information of the product is stored on the server database with the help of IOT and by using this there is no need to scan the same product everytime for inserting the quantity of the product if the product is in bulk, we have to just enter the quantity by using keypad. We are using Arduino uno as our main controller. Arduino uno is a microcontroller based on ATmega328. It has 14 digital IO, 6 analog input with 6 PWM outputs and a 16 MHz crystal oscillator. Connect it to a computer with USB cable. UNO is the latest in series of USB Arduino boards and reference model for Arduino platform.